

Education and Training based on Experiential Learning in Increasing Competency of Health Workers in Public Health Center of South Sulawesi

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The quality of the results of education and training of health workers in general is still inadequate. Ineffective training activities can be seen in the number of complaints from trainees and learning outcomes that are not optimal. The aimed to find out the influence of Experimental Strategy-based training on the Coordination of Health Training Participants.

Materials/Methods: This study used qualitative methods. The informants were 12 trainees. Data collection used in-depth interviews. The tools used were tape recorders, and camcorders.

Results: his study found that the Experiential Learning method is relevant for use in increasing Competency Based Training in a group of health workers (Doctors, Nurses, Midwives, and SKM (Bachelor of Public Health) who come from different functional health positions) at the South Sulawesi Community Health Center.

Conclusion: Competency Based Training for health workers can be done using one method, namely Experimental Learning.

KEYWORDS: Education, Training, Experimental Learning and Competency Based Training

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INTRODUCTION

The transition of epidemiology to diseases and demographics and anticipation of climate change has become a global challenge for the world community in almost every country (1,2). in addition to the challenge of facing competitiveness between countries and between institutions but has become competition between individuals; so that there is a need for coordination and synchronization between ministries/institutions with educational institutions and professional organizations in order to organize education and training especially for health workers (3).

According to (4,5) collaboration is an initiation or activity that aims to strengthen relations between workers who have different professions who work together in partnerships that are characterized by the goals to be achieved together, recognition and respect for their strengths and differences fair and effective decision making, clear and regular communication is established. The performance of an organization will be determined by one of the main elements, namely the quality of human resources (6). The aim of human resource development efforts in the health sector is increasing

performance, providing human resources and professional collaboration in the health sector which in turn is expected to improve health status (7).

Onathan's research in the United States on Health Communication Skills Training for medical assistants for child health services shows; that, 93.5% of trainees considered training programs to be very good, and training could change their perceptions significantly and positively in support of preparation and improvement of child health consultations (8). The implementation of non-quality training will have an impact on the low competency of graduates which ultimately affects the performance of institutions/organizations. According to Mansour (9). the practice of improving the quality of human resources (training, job design, employee skills, employee attitudes, work motivation, etc.) has an impact on the performance of various business units. Similarly, Sule's findings (10) show a significant positive relationship between training and competency-based development and employee performance.

Effective education and training are both abstract and concrete (11). Therefore in this study we will look at the

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contribution of Experiential Learning strategies to the competencies of learning outcomes and training participants' collaboration, Experiential learning is measured by indicators based on concrete experience stages, namely how training participants engage fully in new experiences prioritizing Feeling (feeling) , reflective observation, namely training participants observe and reflect or think about experiences from various aspects prioritizing Watching (observing), abstract conceptualization, namely Diklat Participants creating concepts that integrate their observations into a healthy theory that prioritizes Thinking, and experiment namely Diklat Participants using theory to solve problems and make decisions prioritizing Doing (12, 13, 14, 15).

Studies and several studies on knowledge management relate to variables such as performance, competence, training, learning, and others. Tongsamsi and Tongsamsi (16), Discover the effect of knowledge management and training on manager competencies. Knowledge management has a positive effect on organizational performance. Another study was conducted by Chandavimol, Natakutoong (17), namely the development of a mixed training model by applying the principles of knowledge management and learning actions, to develop the design competency of a health human resource development staff training program in the government sector.

The low level of Indonesian human resources is due to the lack of mastery of science and technology, because of the mental attitude and mastery of science and technology which can be the subjects or reliable development actors. In the framework of globalization, the preparation of education needs to be synergized with the demands of competition. Therefore the dimensions of competitiveness in HR are increasingly becoming an important factor so that efforts to boost the quality of human resources through education are demands that must be put forward.

METHODS

This study aims to discover the effect of the Experiential Learning strategy on the collaboration of participants in health education and training. Based on the conceptual framework, the variables in this study consist of: 1) Experiential Learning Strategies as independent variables, and 2) Education and Training Participants' Competencies and Collaboration as the dependent variable. This study used qualitative methods (18), this is a type of social science research that collects and works with non-numerical data and that seeks to interpret meaning from these data that help understand social life through the study of targeted populations or places. The ethical clearance was obtained from, the University of Hasanuddin Research Ethics Committee (Reference Number:3598/UN4.14.8/TP.02.02/2019).

According to Mansour (2015) (19), in the non-equivalent design there were two groups of subjects who were not randomly selected, one group received treatment and one

group as a control group. In this design the experimental class is taught by the Experiential Learning strategy while the control class is not taught by the Experiential Learning strategy. Both groups obtained a pre-test and post-test. The research design is described as follows.

RESULTS

The results of the interview showed that in depth the health center management learning and comprehension assignments had a positive impact on the participants, thus providing benefits that would be applied in the Puskesmas, learning the management of the puskesmas also opened the horizon which was previously unknown By filling in the worksheets it is very helpful in understanding the management of the puskesmas, learning that is expected to be directly implemented.

1) Informan MA

“With the learning of Community Health Management, it is getting additional benefits that will later benefit from health centers. Very persistent, making it easier for me to remember because of myself who wrote his LK Discussion and simulation of simulated and simulated competence”

2) Informan AMK

“Learning about the management of the clinic is according to the best where direct practice works so immediately understand the Management process (P1-P2-P3). By filling out the LK it is very helpful, where to know the meaning and process, followed by making examples of cases. So the steps are understood. Learning is like the one given by Pak Akhyar because it directly touches on the core of the learning.”

3) Informan HJR

“Puskesmas Management Learning (Planning, Mobilization and Implementation, Monitoring, Control, and Assessment) is that with this learning I understand more about the management of every problem in the community health center starting from the problems obtained, how to solve problems, develop problems (priorities) and analyze problems Learning by completing worksheets (LK) can greatly help me understand Management material at the Puskesmas if I take part in the next training at BBPK Makassar, the learning that I want so that the material given can be easily understood by using a question and answer method and discussion.”

4) Informan MSL

“The system learns interesting because it greatly stimulates participants to study more actively with creative people using active learning aids with methods that facilitate students to understand what material is delivered. It is very helpful because writing an LK report will help participants to remember from the learning material. Interactive learning methods that invite participants to be active and think creatively in the learning process.”

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5) Informan AFT

“After learning to give the impression that our community health center has not implemented a plan that matches the facts. New things about real planning. Providing participants in maximizing activities in the puskesmas. It is very helpful because the active ones are participants & are quickly understood Active Learning Materials.

DEVELOPMENT MODEL

Development of learning devices in this study, using procedural models. According to Setyosari, S. (2016), procedural models are descriptive models that describe the flow or procedural steps that must be followed to produce a particular product. Procedural models are usually found in the learning system design model. In this study, the procedural model used is the Plomp (1974) model in Khonsiatun dan Rahmawati (20).

Figure 1. The Plomp Model (1974)

This model was chosen because it was seen as more flexible and flexible, because at each step it contained development activities that could be adjusted to the characteristics of the study. The Plomp Model consists of the preliminary investigation phase, the design phase (design), the realization/construction phase (realization/ construction), and the test, evaluation and revision phases (test, evaluation and revision), and implementation (implementation)

DISCUSSION

Experiential learning theory forms the basis of experiential learning learning models, developed by David Kolb around the early 1980s. This model emphasizes learning that is holistic in the learning process. Experiential learning, has a role in experience as central to the learning process. Behavioral learning theory that removes the role of subjective experience in the learning process (Kolb, 1984).

..... Very satisfied because in learning the management of the Puskesmas uses methods and media that are easy to understand and can create as desired

The learning process can create a learning process and explore insights into the knowledge of trainees and can develop meaning and give a deep impression of what they have learned. The choice of learning model that can be used to make it happen is by using the experiential learning model.

..... Yes it is very helpful, by using the LK (intervention tool) which is then explained and discussed by all participants, they are active and easily understand how the management materials of the puskesmas are ...

Several studies show the influence of experiential learning strategies on the quality of learning outcomes. The study conducted by Ortega stated that the experimental learning approach can improve understanding of the material and help maintain the information learned (21). Another study found that educational experiences improve thinking skills (22). Other research also provides information beyond the results of service experience, reflection, and the level of involvement and interest, but also contributes to efforts to conceptualize the results and learning process by showing how students understand the new ideas, attitudes, people and experiences they face through experience service (23).

CONCLUSION

Experiential Learning is a holistic and multilateral learning model. This theory emphasizes experience that has an important role in the learning process, which invites participation and activity of participants so that it is suitable for adult learning. Or Education and Training for Health Workers.

Competency Based Training for health workers can be done using one method, namely Experimental Learning. The

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dominant factor determining the success of education and training programs is the quality of learning for itself, in subsequent research The strategies of experiential learning and knowledge management are suggested to be combined because they can facilitate learning well.

REFERENCES

- I. Barrett, Charles, Temte. Climate change, human health, and epidemiological transition. *Preventive medicine*.2015. vol. 70: page 69-75.
- II. Harper, Armelagos. The changing disease-scape in the third epidemiological transition. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 2010.Vol. 7(2):75-79.
- III. Naccarella, Osborne, Brooks. Training a System-Literate Care Coordination Workforce. *Australian Health Review*. 2016. Vol. 40(2):210-216.
- IV. Oandasan, Baker, Barker. Teamwork in Health Care: Promoting Effective Teamwork in Health Care in Canada: Policy Synthesis and Recommendations: Canadian Health Services Research Foundation; 2006. Vol. 1; Page 316-401.
- V. Haines A. Climate Change. The Scientific Basis. Contribution of Working Group 1 to the Third Assessment report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. JT Houghton, Y Ding, DJ Griggs, M Noguer, PJ van der Winden, X Dai. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2001, pp. 881,£ 34.95 (HB). Oxford University Press.
- VI. Parker CL, Barnett DJ, Fewes AL, Blodgett D, Links JM. The Road Map to Preparedness: a Competency-Based Approach to All-Hazards Emergency Readiness Training for the Public Health Workforce. *Public Health Reports*. 2005;120(5):504-14.
- VII. Zurn P, Dal Poz MR, Stilwell B, Adams O. Imbalance in the Health Workforce. *Human resources for health*. 2004;2(1):13.
- VIII. Brown JD, Wissow LS, Cook BL, Longway S, Caffery E, Pefaure C. Mental health communications skills training for medical assistants in pediatric primary care. *The journal of behavioral health services & research*. 2013;40(1):20-35.
- IX. Mansour M. The Practice of Strategic Human Resource Management in a Developing Country. *European Online Journal of Natural and Social Sciences*. 2015;4(3):pp. 500-17.
- X. Sule BA. Effects of Competency Based Management Approaches on Employee Performance in UNHCR Kenya: United States International University-Africa; 2015.
- XI. Piaget J. *The Psychology of Intelligence*: Routledge; 2005.
- XII. Kolb DA. *Experiential Learning: Experience as The Source of Learning and Development*: FT press; 2014.
- XIII. Kolb AY, Kolb DA. Learning Styles and Learning Spaces: Enhancing Experiential Learning in Higher Education. *Academy of management learning & education*. 2005;4(2):193-212.
- XIV. Moon JA. *A handbook of Reflective and Experiential Learning: Theory and Practice*: Routledge; 2013.
- XV. Beard C, Wilson JP. *The Power of Experiential Learning: A Handbook for Trainers and Educators*: ERIC; 2002.
- XVI. Tongsamsi K, Tongsamsi I. Influence of training and knowledge management on competency among quality managers at rajabhat universities in thailand. *Journal of psychological & educational research*. 2015;23(2).
- XVII. Chandavimol P, Natakutoong O, Tantrarungroj P. Blended Training Model With Knowledge Management and Action Learning Principles to Develop Training Program Design Competencies. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*. 2013;3(6):619.
- XVIII. Creswell JW, Creswell JD. *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*: Sage publications; 2017.
- XIX. Setyosari HP. *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan & Pengembangan*: Prenada Media; 2016.
- XX. Khomsiatun S, Retnawati H. Pengembangan Perangkat Pembelajaran dengan Penemuan Terbimbing untuk Meningkatkan Kemampuan Pemecahan Masalah. *Jurnal Riset Pendidikan Matematika*. 2015;2(1):92-106.
- XXI. Ortega K, Murayama W, Holmes L, Taylor S, DePeters E. Experiential learning exercises to enhance learning in a university nutrition course. *The Professional Animal Scientist*. 2011;27(6):591-8.
- XXII. Savage MP, Wehman TL. Assessing the impact of international experiential education on the critical thinking skills and academic performance of college students. *International Journal of Arts & Sciences*. 2014;7(1):1.
- XXIII. Celio CI. *The Effect of Participation in Experiential Learning Programs on Personal and Civic Attitudes*. 2011.